

Empowering Language Learners through Technology -Enhanced Learning

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ABSTRACT

Enhanced learning is seen as an essential element of supporting and enabling pupils to make progress in their learning. The article is devoted to the problem of empowering language learners through technology -enhanced learning. The relevance of this problem lies in the fact that the enhanced learning involves the constant development of the personal effectiveness of today's students, and educational technologies, methods and techniques are designed to prepare students to respond effectively to constant change. The selection of modern educational tools through the principle of interactivity changes the logic of the educational process (learning not from theory to practice, but from the formation of new experience to its theoretical understanding through application), meets the requirements of the time and the challenges facing the educational system.

Keywords: modern educational tools, educational system, enhanced learning.

INTRODUCTION

Enhanced learning is a method of on-demand learning where the environment adapts to the learner. By providing corrections upon request, students can better understand a topic while encouraging discovery and learning.

Technologies incorporating multimedia and interaction have demonstrated educational potential that scientists, teachers and students are embracing. Instead of focusing on memorization, the learner gets an adaptive learning experience based on the current context. Rich content can be dynamically adapted to the learner's natural environment by displaying text, images, video, or even playing audio (music or speech). This additional information is typically displayed in a pop-up window for desktop environments. As well as, interactive educational technologies involve the activity of students in the learning process, allow the most

constructive organization of interpersonal cognitive communication and interaction between subjects, serve to intensify the process of understanding, assimilation and creative transformation of acquired knowledge when solving practical problems, aimed at creating an engaging, motivating, emotionally charged, changing environment and focused on the development of “soft skills”.

Interactive learning presupposes a different logic of the educational process from the traditional one - learning not from theory to practice, but from the formation of new experience to its theoretical understanding through application. Accordingly, the selection of modern educational technologies, methods and techniques through the principle of interactivity, in our opinion, meets the requirements of the time and the challenges facing the educational system [2].

DISCUSSIONS

Modern interactive educational technologies proposed for consideration in the article are problem-based learning technology, contextual learning technology, technology for organizing design and research activities, 4K generation technologies, digital technologies, game technologies.

Problem-based learning technology has enormous educational potential, but its pedagogical capabilities are not fully used in modern educational practice.

The foundations of problem-based learning were laid by the American philosopher and teacher D. Dewey [3], and the didactic aspects of problem-based learning were revealed in the works of I. L. Lerner, M. N. Skatkin [4; 5]. Problem-based learning is a learning process through a system of problem situations, the resolution of which involves independent educational and cognitive activity of students to acquire new knowledge and methods of action with active interaction between the teacher and students. The implementation of this model of interaction, on the one hand, requires a great deal of pedagogical skill and time from the teacher, on the other hand, it causes certain difficulties for the student, who also spends a significant amount of time understanding the problem situation and

searching for solutions. The technology for organizing design and research activities has firmly established itself in educational practice, but it must be remembered that if research activities involve students performing educational research tasks with a previously unknown solution, aimed at creating ideas about an object or phenomenon in the surrounding world under the guidance of a teacher, then project activities involve the presence of a design plan to create a non-existent object/phenomenon and the achievement of the above-mentioned plan by students in the process of implementation with the presentation of the final product [7].

Thus, the result of research activities is the acquisition of new knowledge about existing objects and phenomena, and the result of project activities is the creation of new objects and phenomena. The statement “project = product” is true for understanding the specifics of the technology for organizing project activities.

The variety of approaches to implementing project activities in the context of the educational process allows the teacher to optimally design a lesson taking into account the specifics of project tasks and the project team. In our opinion, greater efficiency is demonstrated by an agile team whose actions are not blocked by excessive regulations on the part of the teacher and whose readiness for changes at any stage of project activity is more important than the initial settings.

These formats prepare today's students for real life and develop self-positioning skills for future professional activities.

Most implementations of enhanced learning are forms of e-learning. In a desktop environment, the learner receives additional contextual information through an on-screen pop-up window, toolbar, or sidebar. As a user navigates a website, email, or document, the learner associates additional information with key text selected using a mouse, touch, or other input device. In mobile environments, enhanced learning is also deployed on tablets and smartphones.

Enhanced learning is closely related to extended intelligence (intelligence enhancement) and enhanced reality. Enhanced intelligence applies information

processing capabilities to enhance the processing capabilities of the human mind through distributed cognition. Enhanced intelligence provides additional support for autonomous intelligence and has a long history of success. Mechanical and electronic devices that function as enhanced intelligence range from abacus, calculators, personal computers and smartphones. Enhanced intelligence software provides additional information related to the user's context. When a person's name appears on the screen, a pop-up window can display the person's organization affiliation, contact information, and recent interactions.

In mobile reality systems, the annotation can be displayed on the learner's individual "heads-up display" or through headphones for audio instructions. For example, apps for Google Glasses can provide video tutorials and interactive links.

Language teachers are also beginning to incorporate extended learning techniques into traditional paper-and-pen exercises. For example, advanced information is presented alongside the core subject, allowing the student to learn how to write story while understanding the meaning of the core characters.

Enhanced learning tools can help students understand problems, obtain relevant information, and solve complex issues by providing additional information at the point of need or "on demand." This contrasts with traditional methods of associative learning, including rote learning, classical conditioning, and observational learning, where learning occurs before the learner has a need to recall or apply what has been learned.

Snyder and Wilson argue that just-in-time training is not enough. Long-term learning requires that ongoing learning be individualized and based on individual competencies and strengths.

Enhanced learning tools were useful for students to gain better understanding of words or understand a foreign language. The interactive, dynamic nature of these on-demand language assistants can provide definitions, sample sentences, and even audible pronunciations. When sentences or blocks of text are selected, the

words are read aloud and the user follows them along with their own text or phonetics. Speech rate monitoring can adapt text-to-speech (TTS) to keep pace with student comprehension.

Critics may view enhanced learning as a crutch that inhibits retention; similar arguments have been made regarding the use of calculators in the past. Just as rote learning is not a substitute for comprehension, extended learning is simply another ability that helps students remember, represent, and process information.

Current research shows that even unconscious visual learning can be effective. Visual stimuli presented as flashes of information showed evidence of learning even when adults were unaware of the stimuli or conditioned rewards.

Extended learning allowed not only students to learn, but also their parents. Tools such as mobile games have helped parents better understand what their child is learning in school. Technology is bringing children's content to a new platform that helps parents make meaningful connections with what their child is learning in school. Moreover, enhanced reality has given young children a new way to learn word articulation. Using marker marks in books read using a tablet, images appear on the screen along with an audio commentary for easier reading.

Enhanced reality has come a long way in the field of science, but is still in its infancy. They started using webcams by having them read a specific marker mark, then an object would appear on the screen that would have the mark on it. Developers continue to gather information about how ER (enhanced reality) can play a role in the learning environment. Over the past few years, technology such as computers, laptops, projectors, whiteboards, and more have been added to the classroom. This allows students to be more involved in what is happening.

Students can now also take notes without listening to what the teacher says, but instead write down what they typed on the projector. Notes may be more detailed and to the point rather than a full explanation. With ER, we can also see images on the board showing students the space between certain objects such as

planets or atoms. There are several reasons why technology-enhanced learning is crucial. It is significant not only because it sets the current bar for education, but also because it has the potential to raise standards.

Students now spend a large portion of their day dealing with technology, making them more tech-savvy than ever. Because of their comfort level and simplicity of use, children nowadays expect to interact with technology, and in fact thrive on it, in a culture where smartphones, tablets, laptops, and other devices are becoming more and more common.

Teachers may take advantage of this growing tech-savvy population by integrating technology into their lessons to enhance connection, engagement, and comprehension in lecture halls and classrooms.

CONCLUSION

Thus, enhanced reality in education can change the time and place of the usual learning process. This style of teaching introduces new teaching methods. With the boom in technology and the largest users in the younger classes, the learning platform has the ability to connect this generation and their smartphones to gain knowledge. Enhanced reality in education, although yet to be fully discovered, is aiming to become a big market.

This style of teaching can attract attention and broaden students' interest in subject matter and topics that are not taught or addressed in a typical classroom lecture. Additional data, such as fun facts, visual models, or historical data about events, can provide a broader understanding of the topics being studied. The learning platform strives to explain abstract concepts, engage and interact with the learner, and discover and learn more information about what they are supposed to learn.

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